
Improvement in Construction Contract Management to Reduce the Construction Waste

Rohan Sawant¹, Shubham Chandgude², Mrunalini Shewale³, Dr. M. Logesh Kumar⁴, Dr. Kanan Thakkar⁵, Dr. G. Chinna Ram⁶

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Dr. D.Y Patil Institute of Technology, Pimpri, Pune, Maharashtra, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Dr. D.Y. Patil Institute of Engineering, Management and Research Akurdi, Pune, Maharashtra, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering Y. B. Patil polytechnic, Akurdi, Pune, Maharashtra, India

⁴Associate professor, Department of Civil engineering, Sona college of Technology, Salem Tamil Nadu, India

⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, School of Engineering & Technology (SoET), DIT University, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India.

⁶Associate professor, Department of physics, Aditya Engineering College, Surampalem

Abstract

The extent of implementation of contractual clauses related to the reduction of construction waste on construction sites has been investigated with the help of several contracts which were incorporated by different government organizations and listed out the clauses that are already mentioned in contracts. In the next process, various solutions and techniques that are being implemented in different countries to reduce construction waste have been found, and have been listed out as a reference by which it is identified whether those solutions can be included as clauses in contracts or not. Interviews with different construction companies' responsible managers were conducted and the solutions have been implemented in the research work. In the final research work, we came up with a solution that has been approved by many responsible managers, and that should be incorporated as a clause in contracts to reduce construction waste.

Keywords- contracts, construction waste, contractual clause, government organizations

INTRODUCTION

The world's urban population is expected to surpass 6 billion by 2045, with cities in Asia and Africa registering the largest growth. The growing urban population has become a catalyst for economic growth, making substantial impact popularly on construction industry. The increasing amount of construction and demolition waste is a pressing issue in many countries due to rapid

economic development and growing populations. Like in India, 14.5 billion tonnes of construction and demolish waste are being generated annually [1]. Construction waste is issue not only in India but it is a worldwide concern, if it is appropriately treated, many benefits can be obtained such as reduce cost, accelerate the construction speed, improve the quality of building and make the people comfortable. The construction wastes are mainly generated due to design errors, improper procurement and planning, inefficient material handling, residues of raw materials and unexpected changes in building design. There are two main contributing factors for construction waste like the waste minimization is not a priority requirement during the project design stage, all the initial design decisions contribute to one third of construction waste. The delays in the project occur due to the time waste in various activity that are the part of construction process. Time waste of particular activity is waste in productive time that could have been productive. Time management in the construction activity is not activity oriented but process oriented. A systematic addition of time waste in various stages of product finally ends up causing significant delay to project. The key to reduce delay is to reduce time waste and the key to reduce delay is in reducing the time waste involved in each and every activity.

In recent years, significant efforts have been made to implement regulations, guidelines and research studies with the purpose of managing construction and demolish waste. It is noted that several clauses in the technical specification and general conditions of contract agreement have impacts on reduction of construction waste. The overall objective is to analyse the impacts of standard contractual clauses in reducing the construction waste. This report is concluded with suggestions to amend the standard Indian contract document to minimize the construction waste in construction industry. This is also suggested that how the construction waste will be represented in contract documents and incorporated into the project [2]. Recycling of the waste is important as the waste has huge impact on natural environment. Harmful chemicals and greenhouse gases are released from rubbish in sites recycling helps to reduce the pollution caused by waste. As the material waste at site may cause the disturbance for worker to work efficiently which may reduce the productivity of the labour [3]. Recycling of the waste is important as the waste has huge impact on natural environment. Harmful chemicals and greenhouse gases are released from rubbish in sites recycling helps to reduce the pollution caused by waste. As the material waste at site may cause the disturbance for worker to work efficiently which may reduce the productivity of the labour.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES:

The aim of this study is to investigate the extent of implementation of contractual clauses related to reduction of construction waste on construction site and changes to the clause contents to make more effective and identify methods to enhance and monitor their implementation.

- To identify the construction waste generated at construction sites from literature review.

- To identify the solution and provide suggestions in terms of contractual clauses which has potential to reduce the construction waste.
- To assess construction waste clauses in selected Indian Standard form of Contracts and comparing the clauses with the solution given in research papers.
- To identify areas of improvement and making suggestions on global practices.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

This study focuses on the various the solutions which we have found out from the research papers are incorporated practically on Indian construction site and the extent of their implementation during the actual practices in construction projects of India. The study also deals with analyzing whether the clients/contractors are using the existing Indian standard contractual clauses and if not, to study the methods which they are practicing.

LITERATURE REVIEW

[4] investigated two cases and results from semi-structured interviews which shed light on some of the major issues, challenges and drivers associated with the implementation of waste management in construction in India. [5] analysed the impacts of standard contractual clauses in generating construction waste and rework in Canada. The paper is concluded with suggestions to amend the standard Canadian contract documents, to minimize rework/waste in construction projects. [6] demonstrated the cost incentive for construction waste minimization for the contractor exists in many instances and will be a factor in future waste management decisions. [7] stated the concept of circular economy (CE) as an approach for waste minimization throughout the overall construction cycle. [8] said that the aim of this study was to see how waste management can be improved in the construction industry and provide research into methods of how waste can be reduced, re-used and recycled. [13] proposed a conceptual C&D waste management framework to maximise the 3R (reduce, reuse and recycle) and minimise the disposal of construction waste by implementing sustainable and comprehensive strategy throughout the lifecycle of construction projects. [16] gave the introduction of new technologies, such as the mechanical saw, that allowed for the increase in the efficiency of time and materials used in construction. [19] revealed that addition of waste plastic strips to fly ash and WRP results in appreciable increase in CBR and scent modulus. The proposed materials can be employed in flexible pavement construction, allowing for the safe and cost-effective disposal of materials that would otherwise be disposed of as garbage. [12] acknowledged the use of various type of buffers to compensate for the uncertainty and absorb the variation with causes. This focus of this research within activity time buffer that is an amount of extra time added to individual task duration to compensate for uncertainty and protect against variation. [10] proposed a model to enhance the performance of the China's construction waste management. The concept contains the following components: implementing government functions, promoting technological innovation, raising employee understanding of environmental protection, reducing site waste, standardising construction waste management, and establishing an

incentive mechanism. [15] puts forward the concept of recycled concrete by thinking of the contradiction of modern building materials subsequently starting from the necessity of recycling waste concrete, it leads to the research systematic condition of the subject at home and overseas. [17] Aimed to verify the technical feasibility of using construction waste as material for the sub base of roads surface. For this purpose, a field study was carried out, which analysed the performance of a surface course base of mix recycled aggregate composed of concrete, asphalt mix, and ceramic material. [13] presented a case study that investigates rebar trim-loss optimization process using an optimization algorithm with structural BIM model. Algorithm makes it possible to use leftover rebar cut off lengths available at site in combination with the market length and special rebar length.

Table 1 Ideas to Reduce Waste Generation Present In Research Papers

Sr. No.	Waste Reduction Ideas	Contractual provision to reduce waste
[4]	Waste quantification, waste segregation, and the implementation of 3Rs (reduce, recycle, and reuse).	The client should look at providing incentives and tender premiums for waste minimisation. Contractor incentives could be an effective motivator in the implementation of trash management in India. This has been demonstrated in other countries, and it is a worthwhile opportunity to capitalise on.
[5]	Exculpatory contractual clauses that are written for the shop drawing review process should be re-evaluated. It may be done by enforcing equal obligations between the main project parties (i.e. designers, main contractors, and construction managers) who review/approve the shop drawings, and the parties that produce shop drawings (i.e. subcontractors, main contractors). The consultants (engineer/architect) or owner should take the responsibility of what they have reviewed and ap-proved, to minimize potential future changes	At present, the general practice is to copy and paste design details and specification from one contract document to another. This practice has high chances to repeat unrelated design components in new projects. Contract documentation and specifications should always be tailored for specific project requirements

[6]	Recycling of construction waste materials	Contractors develop better tools for bid time evaluation so that he must be able to quantify and cost the waste debris that will be generated by sub-contractor as well as price the cost of disposal.
[7]	Concept of circular economy based on a three-layer approach namely micro, meso and macro level for waste minimization	<p>To ensure that there is continuous effort in managing wastes, transforming the procurement methods is imperative at meso level can be done by stating the clauses on the elements of Construction waste mgmt. clearly in the document contracts so that the construction actors are well aware on the importance of implementing proper C&D wastes mgmt.</p> <p>Regulation enhancement can also be beneficial to consider during the building and demolition stages; for example, pay-as-you-throw (PAYT) is an excellent technique in which contractors must pay for the amount of waste produced.</p>
[8]	System of segregation into colour bins was used which varied from different construction site to site.	<p>A well-structured WMP (with help of the BRE online).</p> <p>Agreements between contractors and sub-contractors to determine who is responsible for waste on-site.</p>
[9]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycling/Reuse of Materials. • Addition of Waste plastic strip to fly-ash. • Material can be used in flexible pavement construction leading to safe and economical disposal of material. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of unused materials. • Increases CBR and Secant Modulus. • Disposed as waste. • Promote sustainable development.
[10]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of Government Function. • Promotion of Technology Innovation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote sustainable development. • Promote Non-Pollution.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environment Protection. • Standard construction waste management & incentive mechanism. • Improvement of Technical Condition. • Proper attention to the Construction Process. • Site Waste Minimization Techniques. • Improvement in Technical Conditions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improves Construction Mechanization.
[11]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mechanical Saw. • Lean Construction. 	<p>Increases Efficiency of time and material.</p> <p>Elimination of waste while improving project performance.</p>
[12]	<p>Time Buffer.</p> <p>Last Planner System.</p> <p>Traditional Management of Time Buffer.</p> <p>Percent Plan Completed.</p>	<p>Extra time added during planning of an individual task.</p> <p>Create and maintain reliable workflow between activities.</p> <p>Increases Management Time of Project.</p> <p>Manages Time to Perform a task.</p>
[13]	<p>C&D waste management framework can be prepared to maximise the 3R (reduce, reuse and recycle) and minimise the disposal of construction waste</p>	<p>The sheet of the material which are being used on the site shall be prepared with the possibilities of the reduce, reuse or recycle of the material or whether the material can be disposed by land filling or the incineration like in concrete the aggregate can be used in the road surface.</p>
[14]	<p>Reverse logistics for the reuse and recycle can be used in which the remaining concrete o the site can be return back to the explant for the recycle on the same site.</p>	<p>The process for the reuse of the waste shall be use which includes collection, classification, dismantling process, then remanufacturing of the material and supply to the construction site. By minimizing the cost generated by reverse logistics, greater profits can be made.</p>

[15]	Recycling of the waste concrete	To reuse the waste concrete on the site, Calculate the ration between the recycled aggregates from the concrete to the natural aggregate and then make the evaluation of their economic benefit, social cost benefit and environmental benefit which is economically beneficial for the project.
[16]	Reuse of the construction material like brick in the construction by crushing it, the powder can be used in the mortar and can be used in the preparation of the concrete blocks and also as an aggregate	The used bricks shall be reused in production of concrete blocks, they can be used as concrete aggregate after crushing and the powder of the brick can be used in mortar which reduces the cost of the project.
[17]	Construction waste as material for the base pavement layers of the road surface. The characteristics of the reused aggregate in the pavement construction of the road surface is satisfactory under the traffic conditions also.	Verify the technical viability by using construction waste as material for the base pavement layers of road surfaces by analysing the characteristics of the recycled material on a section of an actual road under real vehicle traffic conditions.
[18]	Give the incentives than penalizing to contractor and on-site waste reduction via promoting professional ethics and motivating stakeholders are determined to be key factors of a successful financial-based incentive plan.	Financial incentive-based plans for the reuse, reduce or recycle of construction waste on the site by the contractor shall be planned by the client rather penalizing for the construction waste.
[19]	a) Increase the use of offsite techniques b) Change in design within particular period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the use of pre-fabricated structural components wherever possible. The use of pre-fabricated materials will reduce the transportation cost of the raw material and also the loss of the raw material during the transportation. • Change in design shall be during the phase when the site clearance or the site mobilization is going on. The major changes should be done in this phase

		only. The minor changes which may not affect the material wastage more can be done during then execution work.
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We studied the literature papers and came up with these following ideas and checked whether following ideas are included in contract where we make contractor obligation which can help in reduction of construction waste. Apart from these suggestions can anymore be included in contract document so as to save time and material waste.

- The maximization of 3R (reduce, reuse and recycle)
- Penalty charges on excessive wastage generated during construction
- Providing incentives and tender premiums by client
- Installation of construction and demolition waste management plant on site
- Percentage wastage criteria on building material
- Designing financial incentive plan for reducing construction waste
- Reverse logistics
- Field rating, stock control to minimize the over ordering
- Environmental education for the work force
- Agreements between contractors and client to determine the appropriate penalty on the responsible person for generation of construction waste
- Improving the labour productivity by using last planner system.
- Disposing off to its where advantageous use
- Waste based management model on construction site
- Standardization of design while initiation, designing and estimation phases.
- Minimising the disposal of construction waste by implementing Standardization of design

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The research methodology involves gathering relevant data by interpreting contract documents through content analysis and by collecting data from Site engineers, Project Managers, Project Engineers, Project Management Trainee and Assistant Project Managers using an interview. The level of implementation of contractual clauses at the construction site were also checked by collecting data from responsible person at site. With the collected data a comparative study and analysis was done.

As a part of our study, we found the wastes which are generated during construction and with the study of research paper we come up with some solutions to reduce these waste .We will compare the solutions from research papers with the Indian standard form of contracts which are based on construction waste and will find whether the clauses of these solutions are provided in the contracts to reduce the construction waste .If not, we will identify and prioritise the most influencing contractual clauses which are not mentioned in Indian standard form of contracts and have potential to reduce construction waste. We will conduct a survey for the suggestions proposed by us to reduce construction waste with the clients, contractors and by conducting questionnaire.

CONTENT ANALYSIS:

Content analysis is used as a research tool which helped us to analyse the actual content of research papers and try to present the content in objective and quantitative manner. It is used to make replicable and valid inferences by proper interpretation. It describes both qualitative and quantitative approaches. It can be applied to examine any piece of writing or occurrence of recorded communication. It is more systematic. Content analysis major purpose is that it helps us to organize and elicit meaning from the data collected and to draw realistic conclusions from them.

Content analysis was performed for collecting data from research papers, Contract documents such as (GCC and SCC) of various clients. As the India is the developing country, many constructions are in progress and which also increases the chances of the construction material waste on the site. To minimize these wastes, many organisations are using the techniques to reduce this waste on the site which is really helpful to the environment also. For knowing the solutions which are being used on the site we have studied the GCC of various government organizations. These organisations are using the solutions such as reuse, reduce and recycle of the material are used. But many organisations are not even using these solutions also. For knowing the more solutions, we have studied the research papers in which they have given the many solutions to reduce the waste generated at the site during the construction phase and many of the contractors are using those solutions on the site apart from reuse, reduce and recycle. CPWD is the organisation who is using most of the solutions from the research papers which we have found out and can be practically implemented on the site.

INTERVIEWS:

The solutions which are implemented by contractors on site to reduce the construction waste are recycle and reuse of the materials generated during the construction. To know more about the practices which are being followed on the site, we have studied the research papers in which we found out more solutions like the provision of penalties to the contractors if wastage is more and also the provision of penalties if any wrong method is used to reduce the construction waste, reverse logistics, maximization of 3R technique, environmental education the labours, standardization of the design, etc. We have also gone through the contract documents of the government organisation to know whether any contractual clause is present in it, but only the clause for reuse and recycle of the material is present. To know whether the solutions which we obtained from the research papers that can be implemented on the site and also if they can be implemented as a contractual clause. So, we have taken the interviews of the contractors and the clients.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

CONTENT ANALYSIS OF CONTRACT DOCUMENTS:

Table No. 2 of clauses present in contract document

Sr. No	Name of Organization	No. of Clauses present in SCF
1	CPWD	2
2	PWD	2
3	NBCC	
4	Bridge and Roof Corporation Limited	3
5	RITES	1
6	SAIL	0
7	NTPC	0
8	INDIAN RAILWAY	1
9	BHEL	0
10	AAI	0
11	IRCON	0
12	Ferro Scrap Limited	1
13	NHAI	0
14	GMRC	0
15	DMRC	0

For the purpose of analysis, contract documents related to General conditions of contract and technical specifications for various government clients from the industrial, infrastructure and commercial sector from the Central Public Procurement Portal were selected using random sampling technique. Government tenders involving all types of projects across India and research papers related to construction waste were taken, availability of clauses which are related to Type of construction waste, reduction of construction waste and Construction waste management in them were analysed.

The availability of clauses in the contract documents were found out by reading through the contract's documents. The key words such as Waste, Reduction, Recycle, Reuse, Debris, Demolition, Bid, Revamp, Materials, Construction, Scrap, Dispose, Excavation, Left-over and searching clauses related them General conditions of contract and technical in specifications regarding construction waste management clause. By doing so a detailed overview of availability of construction waste related clauses in government contract documents was rendered.

Table 2 shows the number of clauses which are present in the general conditions of contract of various government organisations to reduce the construction waste during the execution phase which are mentioned in the research papers. Although there are some solutions given in the research papers which are not followed by the contractors during the construction and they are not even mentioned in the tender document. Most of the organisations like CPWD, PWD, Bridge and Roof Co. Limited India, NBCC, RITES are following the methods to reduce the construction waste. Mostly the CPWD is following the more practices for the waste reduction. A number of clauses are present in different government organisations. We have studied many contracts and we came out with the results that most of the clauses or techniques are mentioned in Bridge & Roof Corporation Limited India.

RESPONDENTS INTERVIEWS:

As the main objective of our study is to suggest the practices to be followed during the planning and execution phase to reduce the material waste which is generated at the site. In the background, we have collected the solutions which the contractor is implementing on the site from the research papers to reduce the waste. To know whether these solutions are being followed on the site or not We have conducted interviews of the Project Manager, Site engineer, Assistant Project Manager, Project Engineer from contracting firms in different project sectors like Real Estate, Infrastructure and Industrial background with a varied range of experience from 1-30 years. From these interviews we got to know the practices which they are following and also whether they are present in the tender document or not. Also, the solutions we got from the research papers are being followed on the site or not and what are the reasons if they are not implementing on the site. We have listed the responses which we got from the site persons and also the percentage of the sector, designation and the year of experience is shown as below,

Basic information:

Respondent No.1		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
29 years	Project manager	Real Estate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementing recycling technique but not mentioned in contract clause. Material can be used accordingly where there is a possibility to reuse eg.:- whatever concrete material is remaining, try to use in road construction to form a base layer. It has mentioned in the clause that every material shall not be use more than its wastage limit. Standardization of design should be mention as clause in contract. Penalties are there, incentives are not mentioned and we have not implemented this in our previous experience as well, but it's a good initiative so that contractor firm will always be aware to reduce construction waste. Reverse logistics is a good technique but somewhat it would be costly in terms of transportation. Instead of reverse logistics if we focus on std. of design, it would be very helpful to reduce construction waste. 		

Respondent No.2		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
7 years	Site engineer	Real Estate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We are using recycling technique but it is not mentioned in the contracts.eg: whatever scraps are generated because of steel bars; we try to use in other construction purpose. Transportation cost will be increased due to reverse logistics technique. Standardization of design will be helpful to reduce construction waste and it also saves time. Penalties are mentioned in the contract clauses but there is no incentive plans to reduce construction waste. Incentives should be implemented in contract clause. Penalty should be imposed on design consultants if they change designs <p>Reverse logistics can be used as an alternative technique but it can't be converting as contract clause.</p>		

Respondent No.3		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
17 years	Assistant Project Manager	Real Estate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We are using 3R technique on site but it is not mentioned in the contract clause and it should be implemented as clause. Whatever scraps are generated by steel bars, we try to reuse in construction work e.g.: steel cutting bars used as shear keys in columns. Standardization of design should be finalized in the planning phase. Penalty charges are mentioned in the clauses but there is no incentive plans for the contractors. Planning is very important. Tender document should be clear and exact according to the design, no further changes should be allowed. Reverse logistics technique would be costly in terms of transportation from manufacturing plant to site. 		

Respondent No.4		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
13 years	Project Manager	Real Estate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temporary road construction work is done by wastage construction material. 		

- We are using 3R technique practically on site but clauses are not mentioned in the contracts.
- No clauses are mentioned for wastage.
- Value engineering for each and every item is to be done clearly.
- No clause are mentioned by the client for standardization of design but is should be implemented as clause to reduce construction waste.
- Incentive and penalty charges should be available as clause in contract and incentives to contractors will be the good initiative to reduce construction waste.
- Proper accuracy should be maintained at every stage of project.
- Daily inspections are important by PMC on site.
- Hire skilled people and give them training that how can we reduce construction waste.
- Reverse logistics can be used as an alternative but can't be implemented as contract clause on it.

Respondent No.5		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
7years	Site Engineer	Real Estate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We reuse demolish waste for filling purpose in the excavation work and it is mentioned in the clause also. • There should be a specific clause is mandatory for incentives. • Reuse of wastage can be implemented as percentage wise in contracts. • There are no clauses are mentioned in contracts for 3R technique but it is the most common process which most of the companies follow practically. • Transportation and manufacturing cost will lead to increase overall budget of project. (Reverse logistics) • We execute every stage of construction work according to our schedule but it's impossible to complete every activity on time so it's not easy to overcome time wastage. • Standardization of design is a useful technique to reduce construction waste and it should be mentioned in clause. • There is no any other technique we follow and no clauses are mentioned in the contracts. 		

Respondent No.6		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
16 years	Project Manager	Real Estate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We are using 3R technique on site but there is no clause on it. 		

- It's a good thought to provide incentive to contractor so that firm will always be aware regarding construction waste.
- Penalty charges are available in the contracts for excessive waste but charges should be mentioned specifically for every material.
- Standardization of design should be finalized in the planning phase.
- Resources and materials accuracy should be finalized in the planning phase.
- Reverse logistics is a lengthy process and it will take too much time which lead to increase duration of project.
- There should be clause in the contract which tells about what activity will complete at what time.
- It's important to provide training program and aware them for construction waste.
- Utilization of waste in the road work e.g.: concrete, steel cutting.

Respondent No.7		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
18 years	Project Manager	Real Estate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We are using 3R technique on site like whatever steel scraps are generated, we use in other work like raft foundation, shear key. • Sometimes whatever construction waste is generated on site, we try to use on other site for better utilization. • 3R technique is the most common process and companies are also preferred but it's important to have clause on it. • There must be have a clause on standardization of design and it is important to finalize every design before the execution. • PMC inspections are extremely important so that contractors will aware at every stage regarding construction waste. • There should be some changes are required on GOOD FOR CONSTRUCTION. • Reverse logistics will too much time in manufacturing or transportation which leads to increase cost and time of project. 		

Respondent No.8		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
15 years	Project Manager	Real Estate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3R implemented on sites but there are no clauses are available in contract. • Whatever material waste is generally generated on site, we try to use that as sub base layer for road construction work. 		

- Standardization of design should be finalized in the planning phase.
- There should be clause in which it is clearly mentioned that if construction drawing will change during execution phase then there will no penalty charges allowed on contractors in terms of time wastage.
- Reverse logistics will not be an effective technique to reduce construction waste because some what it will increase the cost and time of project.
- We can reduce the construction waste with the help of these techniques but it is impossible to finish it.
- Penalties are available but there are no incentive plans for contractor.

Respondent No.9		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
9 years	Project Manager	Real Estate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We mainly focus on those works where we can reuse construction waste.3R technique is not mentioned in the contract but we have implemented in every project. • Penalty charges should be increase so that contractors will be aware more on it. • There should be some incentive in terms of wastage is required for the contractors. • Reverse Logistics can be used but impossible to have clause on it. • Whatever plastics are generated on site, we use in road work or flooring work. • Standardization of design should be finalized in planning phase. • We don't follow any technique to reduce construction waste because some amount of waste will definitely generate but it's important to have some clauses on design, penalties, 3R which would be helpful to reduce waste. 		

Respondent No.10		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
6 years	Project Manager	Industrial
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was observed that due to wastage more consumption of construction materials so we generally tried to reuse construction waste. • Standardization of design should be finalized in planning phase as due to design changes the cost of project kept fluctuating and generated more construction waste. • Agreements between contractor's consultant and client was made to determine the appropriate penalty on the responsible person for generation of construction waste. • Whatever waste was generated on site, was disposed off to its advantageous use. • For e.g. Reinforcement waste was sold in scrap. 		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We don't follow any technique to reduce construction waste because very less amount of waste was generated but it's important to have some clauses on design, penalties, 3R which would be helpful to reduce waste. 		
Respondent No.11		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
8 years	Site Engineer	Real Estate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We don't follow any technique to reduce construction waste because very less amount of waste was generated but it's important to have some clauses on design, penalties, 3R which would be helpful to reduce waste. No contractual clauses are mentioned as well just the material is disposed to its advantageous use. But mentioning of some clauses on design, penalties, 3R will help in reduction of construction waste. 		

Respondent No.12		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
2 years	Project Engineer	Infrastructure
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advantageous use of excessive / over order material. For e.g. RMC is ordered on site and after the activity work the left over material is used in levelling works instead of wasting. In case of steel the cut left over pieces are for fixing of shuttering, bending of formwork and welding purpose. Lump sum project henceforth no concern of client in wastage. Reusing most of the construction materials waste. Agreements between contractor's, consultant and client was made to determine the appropriate penalty on the responsible person for generation of construction waste. Design finalization in planning stage so as to avoid generation of construction waste in future stage. 		

Respondent No.13		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
1year	Project Management Trainee	Real Estate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Neglect the generation of waste though there is going to be some amount of wastage. Recycle of steel in rebar and for concrete we try to reduce/minimize the waste in designing phase itself. 		

- Predefined in contract the percentage of wastage of materials.
- Tender premiums in terms of duration of project
- For e.g. If the estimated project completion time is 12 months at start of the project and if contractor successfully completes it in 11 months then he is paid for the remaining 1 month as well.
- It is mentioned in contract document that for re-work, i.e. drawing related changes client will have to pay contractor.
- Standardization of designs (streamlining during estimation) in the initial phases of construction to avoid wastage or create minimum wastage.
- Environmental education for the work force twice a month.
- Being on client side we focus on labour productivity to achieve timely completion of work.

Respondent No.14		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
2 years	Project Manager	Real Estate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finalization in the design stage so as to reduce waste generation as quality is focused and DLP (Defect liability period is of 10yrs by the company). • Reuse of materials to advantageous use so as to save cost and time. • In case of refurbishment if a PCC is proposed on site, the existing PCC is checked and found in good condition after a certain drill test then, wastage of material can be avoided in these cases. • We focus mostly on quality and sometimes wastage generation is neglected only if it is not in terms of cost. • Turnkey projects so the incurred loss is reimbursed in some another activity to cover up the gained profit. • Activity and capacity building to be done to improve productivity of labours and not practiced on site as it consumes more time and money both which is difficult to implement practically. • Waste material generated is handed over to client/ contractor directly with a checklist, as it is mentioned in contract by government client. 		

Respondent No.15		
Experience	Designation	Project Type
1 year	Site Engineer	Real Estate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dumping of construction waste at a dedicated place and then carried by contractor to reuse and recycle the construction waste. 		

- Percentage waste criteria on construction materials.
- Penalties on excessive wastage generated during construction.
- Reverse logistics method used on construction site.
- Standardization of designs tried but not implemented successfully.
- Double check method implements to avoid over ordering and stock control of materials.

SUMMARY OF INTERVIEWS

The solutions which the contractors are using on site on major level are reuse of the wasted material like whatever concrete material is remaining, they try to use in road construction to form a base layer. In case of steel the cut left over pieces are for fixing of shuttering, bending of formwork and welding purpose. These are some practices which they are following on the site. The most common practice is to reuse and the recycle or the disposal of the material. Also, the solutions like standardization of the design in the initiation phase and the incentive plan for the contractors, are from the research papers and can be implemented on site also can be added as a contractual clause in the contract document as the clause of penalty charges is present in every contract document. The solution of reverse logistics cannot be implemented on the site as the transportation cost is more to return the defective material to the supplier but the material which will be harmful to the environment is to be return to the supplier as it will cause harm to the environment by disposal.

From these interviews the comparison between respondents' practices from different sectors and contractual clauses which are actually implemented, can be implemented in future as well where the clauses are mentioned and clauses are implemented is shown below in figure 4

Fig. 4 Comparison between respondents' practices from different sectors

CONCLUSION

It is found that, the contractors are using the methods like reuse and recycle on the site to reduce the construction waste during construction. Also, in the contract documents of the government organisations like CPWD, RITES, PWD, NBCC, etc. only the clause for these solutions are present. From the research papers it is found that there are more practices like the reverse logistic, incentives to the contractors, standardization of the design, maximization of 3R technique, percentage wastage criteria, environmental education to the labours, field rating, improvement of labour productivity, etc. which are not being used on the site and not present in the contract document of any organisation. But from interview process, it is found out that most of the contractors agreed towards maximization of 3R (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle), Standardization of design, Penalty charges on excessive wastage of material and providing incentives to the contractor can be implemented as a clause in the contract document. As, the transportation cost will be higher the reverse logistics cannot be implemented on site. In terms of construction waste management, the parties which write the contract documents transferred more risk to the other parties through contract clauses. The risks that are mainly outside the contractor's control should be allocated to the client/consultant.

From the data obtained from the interviews, research papers and the contract documents of the government organisation it can be concluded that the solutions which are present in the research papers can be used on the site and can be implemented as a contractual clause in the contract document which are not present in the contract document of the government organisations. The solutions which can implemented on site majorly are given in the following table.

Table 3 Actual contractual clauses present in contract document

Sr. No.	Ideas	Number of SFC having the clause	Clauses present (in %)
1	Waste Management Plant	0	0
2	Percentage wastage criteria	2	15.38
3	Designing financial incentive plan	0	0
4	Reverse Logistics	0	0
5	Field rating, Stock control to minimize	0	0
6	Environmental education for the work force	0	0
7	Appropriate penalty on the responsible person	2	15.38
8	Improving the labour productivity	0	0

9	Disposing off to its where advantageous use	5	38.46
10	3R (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle)	6	46.15
11	Waste based management model	0	0
12	Implementing Standardization of design	0	0
13	Standardization of design	0	0

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

- Client should look at providing incentives and tender premiums for waste minimization.
- Contract documentation and specifications should always be tailored for specific project requirements.
- Contractors develop better tools for bid time evaluation so that he must be able to quantify and cost the waste debris that will be generated by sub-contractor as well as price the cost of disposal.
- Agreements between contractors and sub-contractors to determine who is responsible for construction waste on-site.
- Promote sustainable development.
- The client preferences and enforcement of existing laws could actually facilitate the implementation of waste minimization effectively.

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